

QURILISHDA ISHCHI XODIMLARING XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada, qurilish va ishlab chiqarish sohasida xavfsiz va sog'lom mehnat sharoitlarini yaratib berish uchun mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha amalga oshirilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlarning natijalarini ifodalangan. Shuningdek, maqolada mazkur masala yuzasidan muallif tomonidan shakllantirilgan ilmiy taklif va amaliy tavsiyalar o'z ifodasini topgan.

Kalit so'zlar va iboralar: "Balandlikda ishlash, xavfsizlik, xavf, shaxsiy himoya vasitalari, ish joylarida sanitariya gigiyena, ortiqcha jismoniy zo'riqish va ruhiy charchash".

ENSURING SAFETY OF WORKERS IN CONSTRUCTION

Abstract. In this article, the results of scientific research on the existing problems and their elimination in order to create safe and healthy working conditions in the field of construction and production are expressed. Also, the article contains the scientific proposals and practical recommendations formulated by the author on this issue.

Key words and phrases: "Work at height, safety, risk, personal protective equipment, sanitary hygiene at work, physical overexertion and mental fatigue".

ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ РАБОТНИКОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены результаты научных исследований по существующим проблемам и их устранению в целях создания безопасных и здоровых условий труда в сфере строительства и производства. Также в статье содержатся научные предложения и практические рекомендации, сформулированные автором по данному вопросу.

Ключевые слова и фразы: «Работа на высоте, безопасность, риск, средства индивидуальной защиты, санитарная гигиена на производстве, физическое перенапряжение и умственное утомление».

Kirish.

Dunyodagi barcha davlatlar ham shahar va boshqa aholi yashash manzilgohiga o'ziga xos ulug'vorlik beruvchi binolar qurilishiga alohida e'tibor qaratadi. Sababi dunyoning rivojlangan davlatlari qatoriga kirishda davlat tashkiloti muassalari va aholi uchun qulay turar joy binolarining mavjudligi muhim omildir. Qurilish me'morchilik haqida gap ketar ekan, unda quruvchilar mehnati va xavfsizligini alohida takidlash lozim. Afsuski bugungi kunda ko'pchilik qurilish jarayonlarida ishchilarning hayot xavfsizligi to'la taminlangan deb bo'lmaydi. Biz 20-30 m balandlikda ham quruvchilarning ishonchsiz havozalar ustida, o'ta xavfli sharoitda mehnat qilayotganiga ko'p bora guvohi bo'lganmiz.

Hozirgi kunda O'zbekistonda osmon o'par binolar va massivlar barpo etilyapdi. Bundan ko'rinadiki ishchi kuchiga bo'lgan talablar oshadi, yurtimizda qurilish sohasida faoliyat olib borilayotgan korxonalar kundan kunga, yildan yilga oshib ko'payib bormoqda. Demak ishchi xodim va korxonani xavfsizligi talabi tobora o'sib boradi va texnika xavfsizligi xodimi (oliy ma'lumotli) kerak bo'ladi. Texnika xavfsizligi xodimlari asosiy vazifalari qurilish maydonlarida va uning bilan bog'liq ish jarayonlarida sodir bo'ladigan jarohatlanish va boshqa baxtsizliklarini keltirib chiqaradigan sabablar, bartaraf qilish va tashkilot mamuriyatining ishchi va xizmatchilariga ish sharoitini yaxshilab berish ustida nazoratni o'z qo'liga oladi.

So'ngi 3-yilda qurilish sohasining o'zida ro'y bergan baxtsiz hodisalar oqibatida 119 kishi vafot etgan, 117 kishi jarohatlangan.

Agar xodim baxtsiz hodisa tufayli vafot etgan bo'lsa, bir martalik 6 yillik o'rtacha ish haqi to'lab berilishi kerak. Qaramog'ida farzandllari bo'lsa, marhumning o'rtacha oylik maoshi ularning soniga bo'linadi hamda har bir farzandi 18 yoshga kirguncha to'lab boriladi. Baxtsiz hodisa oqibatida jarohat olgan bo'lsa, bir martalik to'lov bir yillik o'rtacha ish haqini tashkil etishi darkor.

Qurilish tashkilotida bo'ladimi, boshqa korxonada bo'ladimi, agar ish beruvchining fuqorolik javobgarligini majburiy sug'urtalanmagan bo'lsa, turgan gap, baxtsiz hodisani yashirishga urinadi. Ming afsuski, biz bu bilan kurashmoqdamiz, ammo uning samarasi sal pastroq. Buning uchun Buning uchun mehnat muhofazasi qilish sohasini ham raqamlashtiramiz kerak. Bugungi kunda biz, baxtsiz hodisa sodir bo'lgach, uning oqibatini kurashishni boshlaymiz. Lekin, bizning taklifimiz, butun jahonda tatbiq qilingan amaliyot, ya'ni har bir xavf-xatar, baxtsiz hodisa ehtimolini baholangan holda mehnat muhofaza qilishni boshqarish tizimini joriy qilishdir.

Mehnat xavfsizligini taminlash uchun bu mehnat jarayonida odamlar sog'ligini saqlab qolishga qaratilgan bir qator texnikaviy tashkiliy tozalik va davolanish bo'yicha tadbir choralarni

ishlab chiqish va amalda bajarilishini taminlash hamda nazorat qilib borishdan iboratdir. Mehnat xavfsizligini boshqarish va xavfsizligi taminlash quyidagi 10 ta shartni bajarilishini bilan amalga oshiriladi:

- Xavfsiz mehnat qilishga o'rgatish va targ'ibot qilish
- Uskunalarining xavfsizligini taminlash
- Xavfsiz ish uslubini taminlash
- Bino va inshootlarni ustuvorligini taminlash
- Mehnat sharoitini sog'lomlashtirish
- Ishchilarni xavfsiz himoya vositalari bilan taminlash
- Eng qulay mehnat sharoitini va dam olish tartibini joriy qilish
- Kasb kasaligini omillarini nazorat qilish va o'z vaqtida davolanish tashkil etish
- Dam olish sharoitini yaxshilash
- Ishchilarni ixtisosi va malakasiga qarab ishga jalb etish.

Qurilishda ishchi xodimlarning ishiga va ish vazifalariga qarab 3 ga bo'linadi:

1-bevosita quruvchilar

2-qurilish uskunalarini boshqaruvchi ishchilar

3-muhandis va quruvchi ustalar

Qurilishda ishlab chiqarish sanitariyasi tozalik va ozodalik bo'yicha taadbirlaar majmuasi tuzishdan iborat bo'lib maqsadi ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida sog'lom mehnat sharoitini yaratishdir. Quruvchining o'ziga xos jihatlari, ya'ni ish joyining doim o'zgarib turishi, ochiq havoda bo'lishi, bir nechta ish jarayonlarini bajara olishi va boshqalar ish joyida mo'tadil iqlim sharoitini yaratishga imkon bermaydi. Shu sababdan salomatlik va ozodalik quruvchilar uchun ish joylarida ishtimoiy va tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish borasida maxsus uslubiy yo'larni izlashni taqozo qiladi.

Qurilish materialari sanoatida masalan sement, ohak, asfaltbeton va asbofaner ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalarda o'ta zararli chang va bug' zarralari ajralib chiqadiki, ularni albatta tozalagich qurilmalar yordamida havodan ajratib zararsizlantirish zarur bo'ladi.

Xulosa.

Qurilishda ishchi xodimlarni xavfsizligini ta'minlashda birinchi navbatda himoya vositalari va xavfsizlik kamarlari berilishi kerak. Bundan kelib chiqadiki himoya vositalari ham yangi va bardoshligi tekshirilish ham kerak bo'ladi. Qurilishda ishchi xodimlarga eng kerakli himoya vositalarini sanab o'tamiz. Birinchi navbatda hammamiz bilamizki boshimizga kaska kiyish kerak, balandlikda ishlasa xavfsizlik Kamari maxsus qo'lqoplari, maxsus poyafzallar ko'zga yaqol ko'rinadigan formalar va ko'z oynaklar va boshqa himoya vositalari kerak bo'ladi.

Qurilishda ishchilar narvonlar orqali ishlaganda Narvon bilan ishlaganda xavfsizlik qoidalariga amal qilish lozim. Narvon bu xavf tug'diradigan buyumdir standart balandlikda 10 funtdan baland bo'lsa pastda ko'rsatilgan qoidalarga rioya qiling.

- Narvon va tayanch joyi sirpanib ketmasligi uchun tayanch qoplamasi qo'yish kerak bo'ladi
- Narvon o'z vazndan belgilangandan yuqori vazn chiqmasligi kerak bo'ladi.
- Boshni himoya vositasi (himoya kaskasi bo'lishi kerak)
- Sirg'alish oldini olish uchun maxsus etiklar kiyish kerak bo'ladi.

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